

Does weak tie matter for technological innovation? Evidence from patent collaboration network

Keye Wu^{*}, Ziyue Xie^{**}, Tao Wang^{***}, Zihan Zhang^{***} and Li Zhang^{***}

**wky1221@smail.nju.edu.cn*
0000-0001-5345-0791

Laboratory of Data Intelligence and Interdisciplinary Innovation, School of Information Management, Nanjing University, No. 163 Xianlin Avenue, Nanjing, China

***zxie@csu.edu.au*
0000-0003-4741-3016

School of Information Management, Nanjing University, No. 163 Xianlin Avenue, Nanjing, China; School of Information and Communication Studies, Charles Sturt University, Panorama Avenue, NSW 2795, Australia

****ttwang@smail.nju.edu.cn; njuzhangzihan@smail.nju.edu.cn; zlahu@foxmail.com*
0009-0002-5101-2442; 0009-0007-3775-6417; 0000-0003-2104-0194

Laboratory of Data Intelligence and Interdisciplinary Innovation, School of Information Management, Nanjing University, No. 163 Xianlin Avenue, Nanjing, China

Abstract As open innovation is widespread, collaborative R&D has been viewed as a main paradigm for technological innovation. Inspired by the weak tie theory originated from social network, our study tries to figure out weak ties effect in collaborative patent level and examine the contribution of knowledge distance. Relying on the 24,017 collaborative patents in the pharmaceutical field, we constructed the annual patent collaboration network and measured tie strength for each pairwise collaborator. We further quantified patent innovation performance in terms of impact, disruptiveness and market value. The results indicate weak partnerships are conducive to increasing technological disruptiveness, but have limitation in broadening technological impact and market value. Technological inventions generated from strong collaboration could have more technological audience when combining distant knowledge components. Our study not only verifies the weak tie effect in patent collaboration network, but also provides new insights for developing collaborating strategies.

1. Introduction

With the openness of nowadays innovation system, new technological inventions heavily depend on various knowledge inputs and come about by collaborative R&D (Walsh et al., 2016; Xiao et al., 2022). As an important channel of knowledge sharing and exchange between different R&D institutions (Leckel et al., 2020), collaborative R&D can help organizations to actively seek knowledge worldwide and acquire external knowledge, thus increase the opportunity for knowledge recombination and finally lead to technological novelty (De Prato & Nepelski, 2014).

Despite the growing importance of R&D collaborations in open innovation, it is still unclear which kind of collaboration can enhance innovation performance, especially in the individual invention level. Most previous literature takes the perspective of organisation and argues that firms located in the core position of the collaboration network can be more accessible to diverse knowledge and be easier to achieve superior innovation performance (Khanna & Guler, 2022; Guan & Liu, 2016). This stream of studies usually employs network analysis, aggregating the collaboration details into each organization, but ignores the linkage features between collaborated subjects. However, the essence of cooperation is the knowledge exchange channels through which both partners can gain information benefits. The quality of

cooperative outputs depends largely on the intensity and depth of cooperation (Michelfelder & Kratzer, 2013).

Nevertheless, collaborative R&D may not always profit due to the knowledge distance between collaborators (Nambisan, 2013). Based on the knowledge absorption theory (Moreira et al., 2018), diversified knowledge resources from partners may not bring novel recombination as organisations cannot deal with the distant knowledge that is not adaptable to the focal technology. Besides, knowledge distance could also aggravate the transaction costs and communication barriers which are intrinsically existed between collaborators (Dixit, 2003; Wang et al., 2023), especially for those unfamiliar and weak partnerships. Therefore, knowledge distance may be another important factor influencing the relationships between collaboration and innovation performance.

To compensate above research gaps, our study relies on the weak ties theory and focuses on ties strength between technological partners in the collaboration network, investigating its effects on innovation performance at the patent level. The concept of weak ties initially originated from social network (Granovetter, 1973), refers to the infrequent, arms-length relationships which bridge different social communities. Martin Ruef (2002) developed this concept in the field of innovation management and found weak ties are the optimal choice for collaborative entrepreneurship, which could bring non-redundant information and arouse innovative ideas. By taking a more fine-grained insight of technological invention, our study aims at exploring whether there is a weak ties effect in patent collaboration network and reflect in patent innovation performance. The underlying theory is that strong partnerships which has already established the mature knowledge exchange mechanism, may has similar knowledge base that can only be conducive to incremental innovation (Kobarg et al., 2013), while weak partnerships representing as connections between previously unconnected or less-connected organisations, may introduce novel knowledge recombination and nurture the emergence of new technological inventions (Kok et al., 2020). Given the importance of knowledge distance in shaping innovation, we also consider the contribution of knowledge distance between collaborators. Here are our two research questions:

1) Whether and how weak partnerships in the whole technological collaboration network can improve patent innovation performance?

2) What is the role of knowledge distance in the collaboration relationship?

2. Data and Method

To address our research questions, we focus on the collaborative patents in pharmaceutical field, which is a cross-disciplinary field with a high rate of patent collaboration. Specifically, we treat each collaborative patent as the analysis unit, and employ regression analysis to investigate the relationship between collaborative tie strength and patent innovation performance. We also consider the moderator influence of knowledge distance in collaborative patent. All the relevant variables are shown in Table 1.

2.1 Data preparation

As shown in Figure 1, we firstly retrieved all of the granted patents in the pharmaceutical field from the Worldwide Patent Statistical Database (PATSTAT 2023 edition) by constraining the “Technical_Field” as 16. Then, we extracted the patents which have more than one applicant as the collaborative patents. Considering the time lag of patent publication and reserving the

observation windows for calculating patent innovation performance, we further selected patents published before 2015, totally 24,017 collaborative patents as the analysis objects.

Figure 1. Data collection and pre-process

For measuring patent-related indicators, we further retrieved relevant bibliometrics information of each focal patent. As for the tie strength between collaborated applicants, we construct the annually patent collaboration network, in which nodes are the institutions and the edges are the number of collaborated patents co-applied by two institutions. As for the patent innovation performance, we collect backward citation and forward citation information to measure patent impact and patent disruptiveness. As for the knowledge distance, we collect the IPC classification codes assigned for each collaborative patent.

2.2 Variables and measurements

Table 1. Variables and their measurements.

Variables Type	Variable's name	Notation
Independent variable	<i>Weighted tie strength</i>	Considering both linkage weights and common neighbours to depict how strong/weak two collaborated institutions connected, details in independent variable.
Dependent variables	<i>Impact</i>	Number of citations received five years after patent publication
	<i>Disruptiveness</i>	Considering both forward citation and backward citation to show how subsequent patent are influenced by the focal patent, details in dependent variable.
	<i>lg(market_value)</i>	The size of patent family which the collaborative patent belongs to
Moderator variable	<i>Knowledge distance</i>	The distance between IPC classification codes (4-digit) assigned for the collaborative patent
Control variables	<i>Dummy Year</i>	The application year of the focal patent
	<i>Dummy type</i>	The type of patent, e.g. utility model, invention
	<i>Dummy Country</i>	The country/region where the patent is authorized

Dependent variables

As for patent innovation performance, we use three variables to quantify. First of all, we quantify patent impact by forward citation in the five years after the patent has been published (Corredoira & Banerjee, 2015). This index reflects the extent to which subsequent technological inventions are influenced by the focal patent.

Second, we follow the operation of Chen et al. (2019) to measure technological disruptiveness, which not only considers forward citations but also incorporates backward references to depict how subsequent inventions use the focal patent. The formula for measuring patent disruptiveness is defined as: $D = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{n_f^i}{n_f^i + n_{f_r}^i + n_r^i}$, where N denotes the number of references of the focal patent f . For each reference ri , n_f^i counts patents cite the focal patent f but not its prior art ri , $n_{f_r}^i$ counts subsequent patents cite both f and ri , and n_r^i counts patents that only cite ri but not f .

Third, we include the market value of focal patent by calculating the patent family size (Kabore & Park, 2015). Unlike the above-mentioned indexes, this index reveals the popularity of the focal technology all around the world. The more countries and districts in which the focal patent is protected, the more economically value it has.

Independent variables

In order to depict how weak/strong of collaborative relationship is, we rely on the constructed annually collaboration network and calculate the real-time tie strength between two collaborated institutions for each collaborative patent. Specifically, we employ the operation of Saramaki (2007) which takes both local linkage weights and global common neighbours in the collaboration network into consideration. The equation is shown as (1).

$$weighted\ tie\ strength = \sum_{a,b \in P} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_{ab}} w_{bk} + w_{ak}}{s_a + s_b - 2w_{ab}} / C_P^2 \quad (1)$$

For a collaborative patent applied in year t , a and b belong to its co-applicant set P ; s_a/s_b is the node degree of applicant a/b in the collaborative network in year $t-1$, that is, the total number of times that institution $a(b)$ has collaborated with other institutions. n_{ab} is the set of common neighbours between a and b and w_{ak} is the linkage weight between a and one of the common neighbour k with b . Then, we average pairwise institutional tie strength to get the weighted tie strength for each patent. The lower the ties strength, the more likely the focal patent is generated from weak collaboration relationships.

Moderator variable

As our analysis unit is each collaborative patent, we measure the collaborative knowledge distance based on IPC classification codes assigned for the focal patent. Particularly, we employ the operation of Wu et al. (2023) to measure the each pairwise IPC distance by considering all their semantic, occurrence and citation relationship. If the knowledge distance of the collaborative patent is short, it means there is similar knowledge base between collaborators. If the knowledge distance is long, it means the collaborated institutions are positioned in different areas with distinct knowledge.

Control variables

To accurately estimate the effect of weak collaboration ties on patent innovation performance, we further control several cofounders that could potentially impact collaboration performance.

These cofounders are included: (1) the application year of the focal patent, to mitigate the year variance for the patent disruptiveness (Chen et al., 2021). (2) the patent type, such as the invention, utility model, and appearance design, to take the function difference of different patent types into consideration (Heikkilä & Verba, 2018). (3) the country or region where the patent authorized is controlled to eliminate the differences in the collaborative innovation environment (Jeong & Lee, 2015).

2.3 Model selection

Due to the types of three patent innovation indicators being different, we choose appropriate regression models to fit the data. First, the patent impact is a count variable with its distribution is discrete. As its conditional means were smaller than the conditional variances, we adopt the negative binomial model (NBREG) to estimate the coefficient. Second, patent disruptiveness is a continuous variable ranging from 0 to 1, which can be viewed as the probability of subsequent technologies being disrupted by the focal patent. We use a probit model to estimate the effects of collaborative strength on patent disruptiveness. Finally, patent market value is another count variable with its mean is close to its variance after logarithmic operation, conforming to the poisson distribution, so the Poisson model is employed.

3. Result

3.1. Description analysis

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics for variables. As for the patent innovation indicators, the individual collaborative patent can receive an average of 2 forward citations, with a family size of 11 and an average disruptiveness of 0.14. In terms of collaborative tie strength, most of patents are generated from the relatively weak collaboration relationship with an average tie strength of 0.072. And most collaborative patents have a medium level of knowledge distance, reflected in the fact that the mean knowledge distance for collaborative patent is 0.516 with a standard deviation of 0.168.

Table 2. Variables and their measurements.

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
<i>impact</i>	24,017	1.530	4.226	0	111
<i>disruptiveness</i>	24,017	0.143	0.209	0	1
<i>market value</i>	24,017	11.248	11.987	1	119
<i>weighted tie strength</i>	24,017	0.072	0.136	0	1
<i>knowledge distance</i>	24,017	0.516	0.168	1	0.918

Figure 2 depicts the relationship between variables. It gives us the first insight into the weak tie effects on collaborative performance. In which, collaborative tie strength has a positive correlation with patent impact and patent market value, while has a negative relationship with patent disruptiveness. Moreover, the correlations between weighted tie strength, knowledge distance and their interaction term are all under 0.3, meaning there is no multicollinear issue.

Figure 2. The correlation analysis between different variables

3.2. Regression analysis

Table 3 presents the estimated effects of collaborative strength and knowledge recombination on patent innovation performance. By taking patent impact as the dependent variable, column (1) shows *weighted_tie_strength* has a significantly positive effect with patent impact ($\beta = 0.229, p < 0.001$), meaning the stronger collaborative relationships are effective in enlarging the technological impact, rather than weak ties. When it comes to patent disruptiveness (column 3), we found the coefficient for the variable *weighted_tie_strength* turn to be negative and also statistically significant ($\beta = -0.261, p < 0.001$). That is, disruptive technologies are more likely generated from weak collaborative relationships, which verifies our hypothesis about the weak ties effect in the technological collaboration domain. Column 5 provides regression result using *lg(market_value)* as the dependent variable. The efficient for *weighted_tie_strength* is positive at 0.1% significant ($\beta = 0.191, p < 0.001$), suggesting strong collaborative relationships are more conducive to realizing the economic value of technological inventions.

Table 3. Main regression results

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Impact		Disruptiveness		Lg(market value)	
<i>Weighted_tie_strength</i>	0.229*** (0.077)	0.223*** (0.078)	-0.261*** (0.064)	-0.254*** (0.063)	0.191*** (0.034)	0.186*** (0.034)
<i>Knowledge_distance</i>		-0.241*** (0.064)		-0.302*** (0.051)		0.312*** (0.029)
<i>Weighted_tie_strength</i> * <i>Knowledge_distance</i>		1.606*** (0.462)		-0.016 (0.357)		-0.141 (0.199)
<i>Dummy_country</i>	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included
<i>Dummy_type</i>	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included
<i>Dummy_year</i>	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included	Included
Constant	-0.407*** (0.065)	-0.413*** (0.065)	-0.377*** (0.051)	-0.380*** (0.051)	0.887*** (0.027)	0.888*** (0.028)
Observations	24,017	24,017	23,991	23,991	24,017	24,017
Model	NBREG	NBREG	Probit	Probit	Poisson	Poisson
(Pseudo) R2	0.076	0.076	0.083	0.084	0.041	0.043

*** p<0.1, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1;

As for the moderating effect of knowledge distance, the coefficient of interaction term is only significant and positive in column 2 ($\beta = 1.668, p < 0.001$), which takes the patent impact as the dependent variable. The result indicates the positive effect of collaborative strength on patent impact is strengthened when collaborators have different knowledge bases and are dedicated to integrating long-distance knowledge components. As shown in Figure 3, the coefficient of *weighted_tie_strength* upon patent *impact* is the largest in the group of collaborative patents with long knowledge distance. Whereas, the interaction term is not significant in column 4 and 6, meaning there is no moderating effect of knowledge distance on the relationship between collaboration tie strength and patent disruptiveness and patent market value.

—◆— Low knowledge_distance - - - ■ - - - Medium knowledge_distance —▲— High knowledge_distance

Figure 3. The moderating effect of knowledge recombination

To test the robustness of our results, we replace the independent variable by removing the edge weight and only considering the structural similarity between organizations in the collaboration network. The regression results remained consistent with previous findings (see Table 4). The coefficients of *Tie_strength* are negative on patent disruptiveness but positive on patent impact and market value. Knowledge distance only positively moderates the relationship between collaborative tie strength and patent impact.

Table 4. Robustness check results

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Impact		Disruptiveness		Lg(market value)	
<i>Tie_strength</i>	1.677*** (0.307)	1.668*** (0.307)	-0.666*** (0.233)	-0.673*** (0.235)	0.402*** (0.131)	0.392*** (0.131)
<i>Knowledge_distance</i>		-0.244*** (0.064)		-0.263*** (0.050)		0.314*** (0.029)
<i>Tie_strength* Knowledge_distance</i>		5.472*** (1.804)		-0.823 (1.309)		0.486 (0.778)
<i>Control variables</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	-0.409*** (0.065)	-0.413*** (0.065)	-0.231*** (0.037)	0.234*** (0.037)	0.892*** (0.027)	0.893*** (0.027)

Observations	24,017	24,017	23,999	23,999	24,017	24,017
Model	NBREG	NBREG	Probit	Probit	Poisson	Poisson
(Pseudo) R2	0.076	0.076	0.054	0.055	0.041	0.042

*** p<0.1, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1;

4. Discussion and conclusion

Relying on the weak ties theory, this study aimed to examine the influence of technological collaboration strength on patent innovation performance and investigated the moderating role of knowledge distance. We focused on collaborative patents in the pharmaceutical field. We calculated the tie strength between collaborators in the previous year's patent collaboration network and measured patent innovation performance based on backward and forward citations for each patent. The regression results show that collaborative tie strength has a positive relationship with patent impact and market value, while has a negative relationship with patent disruptiveness.

These results suggest weak ties collaboration has a great potential to disrupt the existing technological development, but has difficulty in enlarging the patent impact and patent market value. This conclusion answers our first research question and corresponds to the theory of weak ties (Granovetter, 1973). The weak-connected collaborators may be positioned in different innovation circumstance which possess different and nonredundant knowledge, resources and talents (Ruef, 2002). Thus, their connections may introduce novel knowledge recombination which is unconventional for existing technological systems. The more atypical the knowledge recombination is, the more likely it will change the technological development direction. However, high gain always accompanies with high risk. Such novel knowledge recombination produced by weak collaborations may be not immediately accepted by technological audience due to its disruptive characteristics (Veugelers & Wang, 2019). Moreover, most weak ties collaborations may only manifest as the exploration in certain technological topics and are often characterized as uncertainty, its technological outcome is not mature enough to market.

We also found knowledge distance can strengthen the positive relationship between collaboration ties strength and patent impact. Unlike the previous literature discussion about the effects of technological distance on firm's innovation performance (Zhu et al., 2021), our study takes the perspective of patent and found collaborative patent can reach a wider range of audience when collaborators establish a strong connection and integrate the distant knowledge components. In this relationship, long knowledge distance means each knowledge component has its own technological audience with little overlap, and strong collaboration represents as mature and well-established knowledge integration mechanism which could benefit practitioners in both areas.

Our study not only contributes to the existing literature by verifying the weak ties effect in improving patent disruptiveness, but also provides the practical implications for organizations to effectively select their partners and design their collaboration strategies. Furthermore, our study only considers the weak tie effects in patent collaborative network, but ignores the contribution of knowledge weak ties upon technological innovation. As the knowledge recombination is gradually popular, whether weak ties in knowledge recombination network could also increase technological innovation performance need further study.

Open science practices

The raw data of this study is from Worldwide Patent Statistical Database (PATSTAT, 2023 edition) which is an open-access database that have more than 100 million patent documents from leading industrialised and developing countries. The dataset can be visited through <https://data.epo.org/>. We also provide all the processed data and the source code used in this study which can be available in <https://github.com/wukeye/Does-weak-ties-matter-for-technological-innovation-> .

Author contributions

Keye Wu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft; Ziyue Xie: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing; Tao Wang: Data Curation, Validation; Zihan Zhang: Writing - Review & Editing; Li Zhang: Supervision, Project administration, Validation

Competing interests

No conflict of interest exists in the submission of this paper.

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References

- Chen, J., Shao, D., & Fan, S. (2021). Destabilization and consolidation: Conceptualizing, measuring, and validating the dual characteristics of technology. *Research policy*, 50(1), 104115.
- Corredoira, R. A., & Banerjee, P. M. (2015). Measuring patent's influence on technological evolution: A study of knowledge spanning and subsequent inventive activity. *Research Policy*, 44(2), 508-521.
- De Prato, G., & Nepelski, D. (2014). Global technological collaboration network: Network analysis of international co-inventions. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 39(3), 358-375.
- Dixit, A. (2003). Some lessons from transaction-cost politics for less-developed countries. *Economics & Politics*, 15(2), 107-133.
- Granovetter, M. S. (1973). The strength of weak ties. *American journal of sociology*, 78(6), 1360-1380.
- Guan, J., & Liu, N. (2016). Exploitative and exploratory innovations in knowledge network and collaboration network: A patent analysis in the technological field of nano-energy. *Research policy*, 45(1), 97-112.
- Heikkilä, J., & Verba, M. (2018). The role of utility models in patent filing strategies: evidence from European countries. *Scientometrics*, 116(2), 689-719.
- Jeong, S., & Lee, S. (2015). What drives technology convergence? Exploring the influence of technological and resource allocation contexts. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 36, 78-96.

- Khanna, R., & Guler, I. (2022). Degree assortativity in collaboration networks and invention performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 43(7), 1402-1430.
- Kobarg, S., Stumpf-Wollersheim, J., & Welp, I. M. (2019). More is not always better: Effects of collaboration breadth and depth on radical and incremental innovation performance at the project level. *Research Policy*, 48(1), 1-10.
- Kok, H., Faems, D., & de Faria, P. (2020). Ties that matter: The impact of alliance partner knowledge recombination novelty on knowledge utilization in R&D alliances. *Research Policy*, 49(7), 104011.
- Leckel, A., Veilleux, S., & Dana, L. P. (2020). Local Open Innovation: A means for public policy to increase collaboration for innovation in SMEs. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 153, 119891.
- Michelfelder, I., & Kratzer, J. (2013). Why and how combining strong and weak ties within a single interorganizational R&D collaboration outperforms other collaboration structures. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 30(6), 1159-1177.
- Moreira, S., Markus, A., & Laursen, K. (2018). Knowledge diversity and coordination: The effect of intrafirm inventor task networks on absorption speed. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(9), 2517-2546.
- Nambisan, S. (2013). Industry technical committees, technological distance, and innovation performance. *Research policy*, 42(4), 928-940.
- Ruef, M. (2002). Strong ties, weak ties and islands: structural and cultural predictors of organizational innovation. *Industrial and corporate change*, 11(3), 427-449.
- Saramäki, J., Kivelä, M., Onnela, J. P., Kaski, K., & Kertesz, J. (2007). Generalizations of the clustering coefficient to weighted complex networks. *Physical Review E*, 75(2), 027105.
- Veugelers, R., & Wang, J. (2019). Scientific novelty and technological impact. *Research Policy*, 48(6), 1362-1372.
- Wang, J., Guo, M., Liu, H., & Nie, Y. (2023). Partners' partners matter: the effect of partners' centrality diversity on the focal organization's innovation outputs. *Scientometrics*, 128(3), 1547-1565.
- Walsh, J. P., Lee, Y. N., & Nagaoka, S. (2016). Openness and innovation in the US: Collaboration form, idea generation and implementation. *Research Policy*, 45(8), 1660-1671.
- Wu, K., Kang, L., Xie, Z., Du, J. T., & Sun, J. (2023). Measuring Unequal Knowledge Distance by Network Embedding and Multiple Relationships. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 60(1), 1188-1190.
- Xiao, T., Makhija, M., & Karim, S. (2022). A knowledge recombination perspective of innovation: review and new research directions. *Journal of Management*, 48(6), 1724-1777.

Zhu, S., Hagedoorn, J., Zhang, S., & Liu, F. (2021). Effects of technological distance on innovation performance under heterogeneous technological orientations. *Technovation*, 106, 102301.